

ISic0880

I.Sicily inscription 0880

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Catacomb of S.Giovanni

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 48

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. αἴψα θανῶν μετὰ κῆρα Νικοστράτου
2. ἐνθάδε κεῖμαι
3. αἰαῖ ἀπολλύμενος δεσπότη ἀμφ' ὀδύνη·
4. αὐτοῦ γὰρ γενόμεν καὶ ἐπίτροπος οὖνομα δ' ἦν μοι
5. δαίλαιος Ἀγάθων δακρυόεις ὁ βίος
6. τῆ πρὸ α νωνῶν Φεβρουαρίων
7. μετὰ τὴν ὑπατίαν Ὀνορίου τὸ η καὶ
8. Θεοδοσίου τὸ γ Σεββ(αστῶν)

Apparatus

Text of IG with slight changes

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492510
EDCS 39102037
PHI 140361

Bibliography

- Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0063 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)
- Agnello, S.L. 1953. Silloge di iscrizioni paleocristiane della Sicilia. Rome. At no.100
- Manganaro, G. 1993. Greco nei pagi e latino nelle città della Sicilia romana tra I e VI sec. d.C.. In Calbi, A., Donati, A., Poma, G.(eds.), *l'epigrafia del villaggio*. Faenza. pp. 543-594. At 587 n.132 fig.29 ph
- Wessel, C. 1989. Inscriptiones Graecae Christianae Veteres Occidentis. *Inscriptiones Christianae Italiae*. Bari. At 162

Licensed under a Creative
Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-17): ISic0880. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4339793>